

BENEFITS OF BLENDED LEARNING IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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More and more people worldwide are choosing to learn English. Recent studies show that there are upwards of 1.5 billion English language learners worldwide. This figure covers all ages, from schoolchildren and university learners to young professionals and beyond. There are considerable benefits to learning one or more languages and English learning can be a particularly high priority for individuals in certain industries and locations. How successful is blended learning for languages? Blended learning is a relatively new field that combines traditional teaching approaches with distance and online learning. The use of blended learning has been emphasized that examines the academic and social benefits of this teaching approach. Because it combines traditional and online teaching modes, the promise of blended learning rests on the strengths of both teaching approaches. However, the current scenario requires that we once again highlight this methodology for its ability to solve the situation after the coronavirus pandemic.

Key words: blended learning, synchronous and asynchronous learning, face-to-face, real-time, personal feedback, e-learning language.

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Introduction:

Blended Learning is a teaching approach that combines traditional face-to-face instruction with technology-mediated activities. It provides students to access course materials and interact with their peers and instructors in physical and virtual learning environments. Blended, or hybrid, learning is a type of instructional environment for online students that combines what is called “synchronous” and “asynchronous” learning. What do these terms mean?

Synchronous learning

Synchronous learning means that learners and tutors meet at the same time online via a virtual learning platform (which is often called teaching in “real-time”). They do not have to prepare any classwork outside of the scheduled meeting time.

For example, if you took an hour-long, live English class in which you used video to learn and practice the language with your teacher, you would be in a synchronous learning setting. Tutors provide feedback, but not face-to-face in real-time.

Asynchronous learning

Asynchronous learning means that online students do not meet at a real-time with their teachers; they work offline and do assignments within a deadline set by the tutor. Work is submitted electronically.

As you might imagine, there are benefits to each of these methods for both teachers and students. For that reason, a blend of the two is common.

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Benefits of using blended learning

Is blended learning for languages the best learning English method? We think it can be incredibly effective. Below we have set out four key reasons why.

The first advantage of blended learning is that it allows the use of e-learning tools. English e-learning language tools can be an excellent way to learn. Online learning platform offers an abundance of exercises, built-in self-assessment tools, and revision resources on demand. Many students find that they learn far better when they are able to use online learning tools like these. Furthermore, it is also possible to repeat each lesson or exercise as many times as necessary to polish the learning and correct mistakes. In language learning, revision is very useful when it comes to repeating the new knowledge acquired and there is already software that takes this into account.

Next is that Blended learning promotes students to study on their own terms.

Traditionally learning has taken place in the classroom. Today students have so many resources at their fingertips outside of the classroom that it makes sense for them to be able to tap into these. E-learning software makes it possible for students to take total control over much of their own learning. They can access it wherever and whenever they choose and are no longer limited to making progress during a small window of classroom time. It is the students who decide at what time of the day they advance with the course and without the need to always be physically in the classroom. This way, you can make the most of the times that are most convenient for you, like your commute to work or other classes, to connect and move forward with the syllabus.

Offering precious face-to-face learning time is considered one more benefits of using Blended learning in teaching English. Although technology plays an important role in learning foreign languages, computer software is not as good at reading how a learner is doing as a real-life teacher. Blended learning for languages addresses this by ensuring that learners do get to benefit from presential classes, whether that's in a traditional classroom environment or in a virtual classroom.

With help of Blended learning student have a chance of getting valuable personal feedback. The self-assessment of the exercises speeds up the correction process of the teachers, which provides a very complete and real-time feedback from all the students. It is quite challenging for the teacher to correct each student's assignment individually in a regular classroom setting and for all of the students to participate. Additionally, the tests are conducted on a monthly basis because it would be impossible to correct them otherwise. Online learning provides detailed monitoring of each student automatically, with reports that collect all the information that is generated in the courses and that are generated with a click.

Blended learning is considered beneficial method for teachers too. Traditional learning requires a lot of redundant work. Teachers must continually print handouts, repeat lectures, and perform administrative tasks that, in an online system, might otherwise be automated. Their time should be better spent addressing the unique requirements of each student as they interact with the course material, but instead they are occupied with all of this work.

In a blended learning course, the routine and repetitive tasks are automated or stored in a sharable format. Students can access course materials wherever they are, and teachers are spared unrewarding busy work.

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